

VISITOR AWARENESS OF WORLD HERITAGE EMBLEM IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract: The world heritage emblem is a sign of protection and preservation of destinations recognized as World Heritage sites. However, the World heritage emblem is becoming a promoting brand to pull visitors to the World Heritage sites. This paper aims to examine whether the world heritage emblem communicates any message to domestic visitors to avoid misused and promote the UNESCO emblem's right meaningful. The research context is in developing countries that have an increasing growth rate focus on the tourism-driven economy. The researcher collected data from Vietnam, Philippine, Thailand, and conducted lengthy, semi-structured interviews with visitors at the World Heritage sites. Each interview lasted about 30 minutes with recording and transcribing. The findings could support the local government in promoting UNESCO's right spirit to visitors' awareness and destination management organizations and tourism businesses.

Keywords: Visitor awareness, World Heritage Emblem, Developing countries, Heritage sites

Introduction

There are increasing numbers of world heritage sites worldwide. According to UNESCO statistics, the world currently has 1121 World Heritage sites (as of January 2019: 869 Cultural, 213 Natural, and 39 Mixed). The messages the World Heritage emblem are a symbol of protection, site promotion, and raise awareness of the World Heritage Convention. According to UNESCO, this symbol symbolizes the interdependence of cultural and natural properties, and a central square is a form created by man. The round represents nature, the two being intimately linked (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 2008) (please refer to figure 1 of the emblem design).

Figure 1: World Heritage Emblem

However, it somehow is misused and become a brand for the business. (please refer to figure 2 of some emblem designs worldwide).

Figure 2: Some cases from UNESCO report for misuse

With the conclusion of Conventions Common Services, UNESCO mentioned that "Use logos to promote sites and raise awareness of the World Heritage Convention - Help us controlling *misuses*" (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 2008). Visitor awareness and recognition of the World Heritage emblem were studied in some countries' cases such as Australia, Europe, America, and China (King & Halpenny, (2014); Shen, Schüttemeyer, & Braun (2009), Halpenny, Kono, & Moghimehfar (2018)). These studies are from the most developing areas and countries globally. The researcher used the VOS viewer technique to see the real picture of researching the world Heritage site emblem. An analysis step was applied to understand the research context, using Title-ABS-Key "the world heritage site symbol" with the bibliographic coupling of analysis type and countries unit type, full counting. There was a totaling of twenty-two countries that appeared in the research with threshold from a minimum number of documents of a country is "1", and a minimum number of citations of a country is "0". The result has shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: The World Heritage site symbol and research group in the country unit.

Moreover, in a total of sixty-nine papers written about the world heritage symbol, there were just three papers that had a direct study in World Heritage Emblem in the USA, Australia, and Malaysia. Other research papers on World Heritage site tourism were from Australia, Bulgaria, Canada, China, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, India, Indonesia, Italy, Malaysia, Norway, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Turkey, Uganda, UK, US. This research chose developing countries in Asia with rapid tourism growth for research sample collection to properly understand the bigger picture of the practical and useful World Heritage symbol. According to the UNWTO, the tourist numbers achieved ten percent growth in Asia for the first four months in 2018, the highest compared to other regions worldwide. There were five leading tourist number countries, including: "Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, and the Philippines" (Southeastasiaglobe, 2018). In one forecast report of Asia Pacific Visitor from 2019 to 2023, Vietnam was estimated to be a top tourist destination in the next five years (PATA, 2019).

Thailand, Vietnam, and the Philippines will be chosen as research samples to learn how the WHE was promoted at sites, what the local governments have done to help UNESCO raise visitors' awareness of the World Heritages symbol. As with other green certifications for sustainable business activities, a World Heritage site must conform to UNESCO standards for authenticity and quality. The World Heritage site standard should be promoted sustainably and play a fundamental role in protecting Heritage sites and destinations (IUCN, 2013). The World Heritage emblem symbolizes Man and Nature's interaction, representing properties protected by the World Heritage Convention. Some tourism companies use the emblem as products or souvenirs with commercial use but free gifting. Local governments have placed it as a road sign which indicates ways to arrive at the World Heritage site, signs within sites (e.g., information stands, pathways, walkways, building signs). The UNESCO published the World Heritage symbol's operational guidelines to site governance (UNESCO, 1978). The study objective is to learn what visitors aware of the World Heritage symbol in their mind for WHS's right promotional strategy for the sustainable tourism future in the developing countries. The finding that could support local government to promote UNESCO's right spirit to visitor's awareness.

Literature Review

UNESCO is the organization seeking to identify, protect, and preserve the culture and natural heritage worldwide. UNESCO helps local communities understand heritage value and meaning to their life. World Heritage sites have become so popular as a brand or trademark for visitors and attracted more and more visitors at sites. According to UNESCO (2010), the term "heritage" appears as a legacy system from the past, what we live today, and what we pass on to future generations. With the number of world heritage sites worldwide increasing, preservation has become an urgent mission that UNESCO should consider to ensure protection, encourage the country in adhering to the world heritage convention, and help countries by providing technical assistance and professional training.

Many definitions of heritage are about cultural, natural, and mixed sites (UNESCO, 1978). A world Heritage which is defined by both Eco and cultural tourism (Pedersen, 2002), as a product shaped from history (Timothy & Boyd, 2006), as something passed on from the predecessor (Webster, 2004). Being UNWTO inscribed in the world heritage list has brought a coveted brand to the tourism destination and an effort to market itself as a tourist destination (Hall & Piggin, 2012). The countries seek World Heritage site designation because they lead to greater awareness of the site value and improved measures to preserve and protect them (e.g., Wang, 2007). Other studies suggest that being recognized in the World Heritage List will provide tourism destinations with intensified assistance from local, national governments, and international organizations (Winter, 2007; Hazen, 2008). From the beginning, UNESCO did not intend to recognize the system of accreditation for tourism marketers, and the purpose of

the designation is protection and sustainability, as well as increasing cultural and natural values awareness from the community. However, in the eyes of tourism marketers and travel agencies, the WHS brand becomes the primary attractions to promote as must-see places or pull factors to attract visitors (G. Yan et al., 2007). In terms of customers or visitors, the brand will refer to brand equity, which is the brand's importance in the customer's eyes (Aaker, 1996). The researcher used the brand equity literature because the research aim is about visitors' perception understanding that brand equity is a marketing term determined by consumers' perception of and experiences with the brand (Godey et al., 2016).

Over the past few years, brand equity has received the attention from marketing research (Lassar, Mittal, & Sharma, 1995; Cobb-Walgren, Ruble, & Donthu, 1995; Pitta & Katsanis, 1995; Erdem & Swait, 1998; Berry, 2000). Initially, Farquhar (1989) recognized brand equity, and it is vital as it influences business performance in long-term cash flows and future profits (Motameni & Shahrokhi, 1998; Tiwari, 2010). It allows the company to more effectively engage with their customer database in such a way that drives consumer perceptions of preference and purchase intention (Cobb-Walgren, Ruble, & Donthu, 1995b; Chen & Chang, 2008; Chang & Liu, 2009), builds relation to customers via product quality (Herrmann et al., 2007) and importance to customer loyalty or brand loyalty (Taylor et al., 2004).

Brand equity comprises two different research perspectives, including financial and customer perspectives (Keller, 1993). From an economic standpoint, brand equity is measured by companies' asset market value (Simon & Sullivan, 1993; Farquhar, 1989). From the customer perspective, Brand equity is appraised according to the consumer's reaction to a brand name (Shocker, 1988). Customer perspective towards brand equity is divided into consumer behavior (Farquhar, 1989) and consumer perception (Mahajan et al., 1994). Based on Mahajan et al. (1994) findings, consumer perception can evaluate customer-based brand equity. There are different dimensions of brand equity concept from other researchers. (Please see table 1).

Table .1. The Concept of Brand Equity

<i>Researchers</i>	Brand equity definitions
<i>(Smith & Aaker, 1992; Aaker, 1996) and (K. L. Keller, 1993; 2003)</i>	The aspirational self-image, customers' perceived quality, brand awareness, brand association, and brand loyalty
<i>(Farquhar, 1991) and (Simon & Sullivan, 1993a)</i>	Financial perspective (the market value of a company's asset)
<i>(Keller, 1993)</i>	From a customer perspective, brand equity is appraised according to the consumer's reaction to a brand name
<i>(Lassar et al., 1995b)</i>	Financial perspective and customer perspective
<i>(Prasad & Dev, 2000)</i>	Brand performance and brand awareness
<i>(Pride & Ferrell, 2003)</i>	Brand assets, Brand awareness, Brand loyalty, Perceived brand quality, Brand associations.

However, this paper will adopt customer perspective-based brand equity by stressing two elements: brand image and brand awareness (Keller, 1993). Smith & Aaker (1992) suggests that brand equity in tourism is composed of brand awareness (recall and recognition) and brand image (attributes, benefits, and attitudes) (Keller, 1993). The brand recall relates to customer retrieving of a particular product or the needs from a given category or some type of probe (Keller, 1993). Some types of probe to test the awareness is sudden without

premeditation or external stimulus (e.g., What is the first name recalled in your mind? ... or top-of-mind tests). Brand awareness at the recognition level is prior knowledge about a product which consumer to recognize one brand over other brands (name, visual symbols).

The brand image, which Keller (1993) posed, can be classified into attributes, benefits, and attitudes that customers link to the brand. Brand image theory is critical to marketing strategy and brand recognition or position in customers' minds (Keller, 2003). Park (1986) had an expression of a brand concept that can be either symbolic (intangible features) attributes or functional (tangible features). They are understandable in the customer benefits context to satisfy their immediate and practical needs (Functional) or for self-expression and prestige needs (Symbolic). Tourism products seem both have two types of features; visitors choose to visit a specific destination for their particular needs, such as climate, amenities, and cultural attributes. However, the list of destinations that belongs to some probe of attributes, such as the emergence of the site as a fashion accessory they would like to have, the pictures and videos from the place they visited, often used to show others in social networks. Visitors' willingness for their trips as expressive devices shows their self-actualization needs (Caldwell & Freire, 2004).

WHS's awareness did motivate visitors to come, but it did not appear to be a powerful influence (C. Yan & Morrison, 2008). Dewar et al. (2012) found that only 94 of 389 (24%) of those surveyed could recall what the World Heritage emblem represented. According to Timothy & Boyd (2006), Heritage tourism is the oldest and most popular type of tourism. The motivation to travel to heritage tourism is based on visitors' perception of their favorite heritage sites (Chen & Chen, 2010). Visitors seek more authentic and value-added experiences at the heritage site than mass destinations or traditional tourism products (sea, sun, sand). The heritage attributes towards their background and recreational experiences, at the same time, to increase the returning visitor rate (Yankholmes & Akyeampong, 2010). Based on the conclusion of Poria, Butler, & Airey (2004) research, the visitor reasons to visit heritage sites are the willingness to learn, desire to be entertained, and willingness to be exposed to an emotional experience, heritage experience, learning experience, and recreational experience. The same findings for WHS visiting motivation in Portalés et al., (2009) research are the opportunity to see exciting things and the desire to learn more about the local culture. The seeking motivation to visit the heritage site is all about leisure, culture, education, and social interaction experiment (Chen & Chen, 2010). Goh (2010) research findings show that education value, learning, positive feedback from previous tourists, and the site's well-known reputation are reasons for visitation.

The target market to World heritage sites including young and well educated (Vareiro et al., 2013), high educated, high income and spend more time and money on their vacation (Silberberg, 1995), independent visitors, travel party, region, trip type are kinds of visitors who were knowledgeable of the destination's World Heritage status (C. Yan & Morrison, 2008). The visitors who can recognize the WHS symbol have the level of education from secondary school, university graduate, and Master's or Ph.D. (Dewar et al., 2012).

Methodology

We conducted lengthy, semi-structured interviews with domestic visitors at the World Heritage sites to understand visitors' perceptions of the World Heritage site emblem in the research phenomenon. Some research issues should base on observation reliably in systematic empirical research and could not be seen through quantitative data. Each interview lasted about 30 minutes with recording and transcribing. Recording interviews allow researchers to focus on the content of conversations and then ask questions or clarify where essential to avoid distraction during interviews due to researchers' note-taking (Kvale & Brinkmann, 2009).

Linguistic and cultural differences can impede comprehension among interviewees and interviewers, leading to several challenges in obtaining information during interviews.

This research divided the content analysis process into two stages: "The first stage dealt with single interview transcripts, the second stage is the content analysis and aimed at the integration of all the individual factors, variables, and links from all interviews, in order to collect all themes for answering research questions."

Participants

The study explores World Heritage awareness and compares it among three developing countries (Vietnam, Thailand, and the Philippine). The research's primary purpose is about WHS designation awareness, so the informant will be visitors who can identify a WH logo. After greeting, the interviewer will start with a question: *'Have you ever heard about the term World Heritage Site and seen this symbol?'* If the answer was 'No,' the informants will be eliminated from the study (C. Yan & Morrison, 2008). We met 80 visitors at the heritage sites; only 30 knew about World Heritage sites and had answers ("Yes, I know), accounting for 37.5% of the total respondents. Including 12 Filipinos, 7 Thai, 11 Vietnamese.

Data Collection and Analysis

Qualitative techniques allow researchers to build and examine qualitative databases; some techniques are available, such as analyzing interview transcripts (Burnatd, 1991), photographs (MacKay & Couldwell, 2004), multimedia (Viken, 2006), or the internet websites (Davidson & Yu, 2008). This research includes open-ended questions to explain the phenomenon under study, and the data is derived from interview transcripts. All interviewees code according to their nationality and took the serial number according to the total number of participants. Accordingly, 11 Filipino (FL) got labels from FL1 – FL11; 11 Vietnamese (VN) got labels from VN1 - VN11; 11 Thailand (TL) got labels from TL1 - TL11. The research objective is to explore awareness of the WHS title and its emblem. Some questionnaires will be revised from the literature review to suit the research context in three countries (please see Table 2 below).

Table.2. Interview Questions for Research Context

<i>Literature Review</i>	Source	Questions for research
<i>Explore awareness of the WHS title and its logo</i>	(Poria et al., 2011)	Does the visitor know this logo? Did the visitor remember seeing the brand somewhere before or during their visit?
<i>Some awareness, recognition, and recall of World Heritage status and symbol variables: First-time, return, frequent local visitor Recognized the WH symbol Correctly recalled what the WH symbol represents</i>	(King & Halpenny, 2014)	Some awareness, recognition, and recall of World Heritage status and symbol variables for Hoi An: - First-time, return, frequent local visitor - Recognized the WH symbol - Correctly recalled what the WH symbol represents
<i>Informants' perception of World Heritage sites and their expectation of visiting such sites</i>	(Poria et al., 2011)	What does the WHS status mean to the visitor? (Omar et al., 2013)

Based on the literature review, the questions for the interviewees are:

1. “Have you ever heard of the term World Heritage Site and seen this emblem?”
2. “How do you know about this symbol?”
3. “What is the first name recalled in your mind when you see this emblem?”
4. “What does the WH symbol represent?”
5. “How are the first images of this emblem link to your mind? (attributes, benefits, and attitudes)”

Findings

Of the 80 visitors asked, only 30 knew and saw this symbol. The interview results collected based on 30 visitors knew the logo and agreed to participate in the interview. The average interview time per person (seconds/ 1 person) as follows: Thais with 1498 seconds, Vietnamese with 3415 seconds, and Filipino with 1753 seconds. For the first question to get to know the visitors' awareness about the World Heritage logo, we have some findings.

Question number 1: “What is the first name recalled in your mind when you see this symbol?”

Table.3. The Name Recalled in their Minds with Appearance Times

<i>Term to be recalled in their minds</i>	Number of times mentioned
<i>World Heritage</i>	(2)
<i>UNESCO</i>	(2)
<i>None</i>	(2)
<i>World Heritage UNESCO</i>	(1)
<i>World Heritage Site Certificate</i>	(1)
<i>World Heritage Logo</i>	(1)
<i>World Heritage Emblem</i>	(1)
<i>Wall and protect something</i>	(1)
<i>Tourism and culture</i>	(1)
<i>The square represents the masterpiece created by humanity, while the circle represents nature and the Earth; it shows a respectful attitude to protect humanity's heritage. Square and circle are connected to show harmony and unity.</i>	(1)
<i>The first name recalled in my mind is Thai heritage's Historic city of Ayutthaya.</i>	(1)
<i>The coin</i>	(1)
<i>Something is relative to tourism</i>	(1)
<i>Patrimonio</i>	(1)
<i>Maybe a traffic sign</i>	(1)
<i>I have no idea</i>	(1)
<i>Tourist city</i>	(1)
<i>Ancient Town</i>	(1)
<i>A picture of two hands covering something</i>	(1)
<i>Have no idea</i>	(1)
<i>Ancient coins; traffic warning signs.</i>	(1)
<i>The first time for me to learn about this logo</i>	(1)

Nine people spoke roughly about the logo that they saw. The terms that they mentioned included WHS, UNESCO, WH symbol. The remaining 18 people have no idea what the WH symbol is and do not know its meanings. They used the words to express their understanding of that symbol with the following terms: "*wall to protect something, tourist and culture, history, coin, tourist city, hands and have no idea.*" Those who answered the correct terms know that the logo represents a world cultural heritage of UNESCO. The researcher tried to fully understand the respondents' thoughts on the symbol by asking two almost identical questions about the meaning to ensure that the informants understood the interview's purpose. Those two questions are, "What is the first name recalled in your mind when you see this emblem?" and "What does the WH symbol represent?"

Question number 2: "What does the WH symbol represent?"

Table.4. The WH Symbol Represent

<i>You are driving into/coming into a plaza</i>	(1)
<i>World Heritage Tourism Icon</i>	(1)
<i>World Heritage Site Certificate</i>	(1)
<i>World heritage</i>	(1)
<i>UNESCO world heritage symbol</i>	(1)
<i>UNESCO</i>	(1)
<i>Unaware</i>	(1)
<i>It represents the interdependence of the world's natural and cultural diversity</i>	(1)
<i>The symbol represents to protect all about the heritage in the world.</i>	(1)
<i>Save and protect</i>	(1)
<i>It represents the interdependence of the world's natural and cultural diversity</i>	(1)
<i>Pagoda Bridge</i>	(1)
<i>Pagoda</i>	(1)
<i>I do not know.</i>	(1)
<i>I do not know</i>	(1)
<i>Bridge Pagoda</i>	(1)
<i>History</i>	(1)
<i>Heritage sites</i>	(1)
<i>Do not know</i>	(1)
<i>Do not know</i>	(1)
<i>The World Heritage</i>	(1)
<i>Cultural heritage</i>	(1)
<i>An attraction where belongs to protecting</i>	(1)
<i>A diamond-shaped structure that represents a building or structure</i>	(1)
<i>It is the first time for me to learn about this logo</i>	(1)

The results show that the answers are almost the same, informants who know a symbol giving the correct and identical answers to two questions. The informants who have heard about the World Heritage Site but have not seen the logo will share options or images that appeared in their minds when answering the interview.

Question number 3: "How are the first images of this symbol link to your mind?" Various informants who know the symbol will have their answers with the words cultural or sign of protection. Others who did not know the symbol will share the image that appeared in their

minds, such as “the ancient town, tourist city, and historical place.” Some answers are "no idea, I do not know, or nothing comes to mind unless a search engine.” (Please see Table 5 below).

Table.5. Brand Image

<i>Attributes</i>	<i>Benefits</i>	<i>Attitude</i>
<i>Symbolic Attributes: Cultural, self-actualization, social.</i> <i>Functional: World heritage sites</i>	To learn history, culture, explore world heritage.	The logo brings to mind a sense of heritage protection.
<i>Brand awareness</i>		
<i>Recall (top-of-mind tests)</i>	<i>Recognition (is prior knowledge about a product which consumer to recognize one brand over other brands)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>World heritage sites,</i> <li style="padding-left: 20px;">- <i>UNESCO,</i> <li style="padding-left: 20px;">- <i>Pagoda,</i> <li style="padding-left: 20px;">- <i>Cultural,</i> <li style="padding-left: 20px;">- <i>Natural,</i> - <i>A specific tourism area,</i> - <i>The historic properties protected by the World Heritage Convention,</i> - <i>A symbol of preservation for the next generation,</i> <li style="padding-left: 20px;">- <i>History Place.</i> <i>Nothing comes to mind unless a search engine used</i>	World heritage sites only Preservation, Protection, Environment;	

WHS emblem image is more diverse in terms of attributes than benefits and attitudes. Most customers remember WHSE associated with the image of destinations such as temples, monuments, pagoda, historic properties, or even UNESCO.

Question number 4: How do you know about this symbol?

Table.6. Visitors Know the WHS Emblem Through

<i>Options</i>	<i>Responses</i>
<i>UNESCO</i>	8
<i>This interview</i>	8
<i>Website</i>	1
<i>Tourism Advertising</i>	6
<i>Friends and relatives</i>	4
<i>Social media</i>	2
<i>Newspapers</i>	1
<i>Celebrities</i>	0

Most visitors know more about the WHS emblem through UNESCO than from other sources.

Some answer that "Unaware, Travel, through this survey, through surfing, pagoda, no idea, I am not familiar with this symbol, I am not familiar with this symbol, I have seen in the UNESCO website, friend, the first time seeing this.

During the data analysis, some demographic information was collected. (please see Table 7 below)

Table .7. Informants' demographic

<i>Nationality</i>	No
Filipino	12
Vietnam	11
Thailand	7
<i>Gender</i>	
Male	15
Female	15
<i>Age</i>	
20–29	11
40–49	11
30–39	6
16–19	1
50–59	1
<i>Marital Status</i>	
Single	18
Married	12
<i>Occupations (Job/ Career)</i>	
IT	5
Student	5
University Administrator	1
Tourist Guide	1
Teacher	1
Teaching	1
Teacher assistance.	1
Teacher	1
Staff	1
Sales	1
RND	1
Official government	1
Master Student	1
IT professional	1
Intern	1
Instructor	1
Full-Time Ph.D. student	1
Educator	1
Caregiver	1
Businessman	1
Banker	1
Assistant Professor	1

Research shows that visitors' background to WHS is diverse, well-educated, and most of them young and single.

Conclusion and Discussion

This paper examines whether the World Heritage brand communicates any message in developing countries to domestic visitors. The data was collected in Vietnam, Philippine, Thailand to learn whether the World Heritage brand and visitor awareness of UNESCO's World Heritage symbol is connected. The image that is recalled in their mind is some old things or others, such as traffic signs or traffic warning signs. Some answered that they have no idea, and it is the first time to know about this logo. The number of people who know the meaning of the world heritage emblem is tiny, they have heard about the World Heritage site, but they learn nothing more than a famous tourist attraction or just a heritage place. The small group of informants knew it as a symbol of cultural or the sign of Heritage protection. Their first thoughts were ancient ruins or historical places. Only very few people mentioned signs of tourism and preserving monuments when visiting. Some answers are, "nothing comes to mind unless a search engine is used."

A few people know this symbol from UNESCO websites, from this interview, some tourism advertisings. The age of visitors to the WHS is mainly from 20 to 49, mostly single, hanging out with friends and lovers. They are students and workers in professions such as teachers, university administrators, tour guides, teachers, staff, sales coordinators, research and development coordinator, government officer, master student, information technology officer, intern, instructor, Ph.D. student, educator, caregiver, businessman, banker, assistant professor. Visitors who travel to World Heritage sites are mostly highly educated. Still, the WHS information interacting with them during the tour is not much except for the sights' regulations. Few people understand that visitors need to combine tourism and conservation at visiting sites. Few people see World Heritage sites' emblem on the way to the Heritage sites.

The research findings reflect that visitors did not have enough information about the WHS emblem and its meaning. The local governments did not implement properly to promote the right UNESCO spirit for WHS designation. UNESCO and local governments or DMO (Destination marketing organization) should have more detailed guidance and plans to visitors and locals by specific communications as follows:

- According to UNESCO's guidelines of the World Heritage emblem, which should be on the highway entering the Heritage sites, not all the World Heritage sites do it that way.
- Radio became a powerful propaganda tool to communicate and change visitors' behaviors at WH sites.
- Raise awareness of waste sorting and disposal in the right place, do not touch objects, and respect the instructions at the WH sites.
- DMO should re-set the rules and earnestly implement them with a clear reward and punishment regime to better preserve the heritage.
- The WHS logo should be designed following UNESCO regulations without misused.
- Tour companies must send brief direction of WH sites' right behaviors to visitors before the tours begin.
- Tour guides should be required to inform visitors about the right behaviors at WH sites before providing any assistance on cultural, historical information, or other significant interest.
- Local government should propagate the right behavior of language, costumes, and social practices accordingly.
- Combined with propaganda is sanctions against offensive actions, acts of infringing upon world heritage areas. The government must have precise regulations supporting propaganda of the right behaviors at the heritage site for tourism businesses.

The finding that could support local government to promote UNESCO's right spirit to visitors. Similar research findings outside Asia such as Queensland, Australia, Hawaii, USA visitors could not recall what the World Heritage emblem represented (King & Halpenny, (2014); Shen, Schüttemeyer, & Braun (2009), Halpenny, Kono, & Moghimehfar (2018). The locals are proud of their World Heritage site's status and build many policies to promote and attract more visitors to sites. Still, there are no proper solutions associated with the heritage conservation plan for the visitors' role. The research has already brought a relatively complete picture of tourists' perceptions of WHS and WH Symbol around the world. The local government should raise awareness and build appropriate regulations required for each destination and its status to continue maintaining for the next generation in terms of our nation's culture and history.

Limitation and Future Research

This research contributes to an empirical and practical approach in interviewing the visitors at the World Heritage sites in three countries to understand the WHSD's meaning in the rest of the world map piece. The research approach still has some limitations, such as the sample collected in the center of cities with many visitors. Other researchers can collect data outside the city with the WHS for future research and choose larger representatives and conduct quantitative surveys to recognize the differentiates among groups.

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